

Supplementary Data.pdf

Article “Developing a digital solution for community-led initiatives: from local agents needs to interface design”

TABLE I. MEDIATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Categories	FG1	FG2
<u>Dissemination tools</u> (e.g. Facebook, LinkedIn, website, print materials/flyers, virtual agendas, post)	39	15
<u>Communication tools</u> (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, SMS, Email, telephone)	17	25
<u>Tools to gather feedback</u> (e.g. Rating and review tools/Google Maps/TripAdvisor/Facebook Reviews, Paper questionnaires, Own tools)	9	1
<u>Productivity tools</u> (e.g. Storage/Dropbox, mailing-lists/MailChimp)	8	5
Context of use		
Within members of the initiative	9	16
External actors	39	25

TABLE II. PURPOSES OF USE OF DIGITAL TOOLS

Categories	FG1	FG2
Keep community members in touch (e.g. Email, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Phone)	3	3
Promote the initiative (e.g. Websites, Facebook, SMS, Posters, Mailing lists, TripAdvisor, Facebook Reviews)	16	12
Gather feedback (e.g. TripAdvisor, Facebook Reviews, Own tools)	4	1
Management activities within initiative (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Email, Google Drive, Website, Virtual Agendas)	5	11
Information sharing (e.g. Personal contact network, Posters, Facebook, Blogs, Website, Google Drive, E-mail, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger)	9	4
Amplify information reach (e.g. Facebook, Flyers, TV)	4	0
Link-up with other actors (e.g. Email, Phone)	3	1
List events taking place (e.g. Facebook, Posters)	7	1
Endorsement	8	0
Context of use		
Within members of the initiative	5	16
External actors	8	9

TABLE III. TYPE OF EXPERIENCE PROMPTED BY TECHNOLOGY USE

Categories	FG1	FG2
Negative		
Excess of unsorted information (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, SMS, E-mail, Website, Facebook, Virtual agendas)	15	7
Impersonal communication	---	5
Too many digital tools (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Slack, Email, Skype, GoToMeeting, GoogleMaps, Facebook Reviews)	10	9
Complexity (e.g. Tools to create websites, Photoshop, MailChimp)	3	---
Unmet extectations (e.g. Facebook Events)	---	5
Positive		

<i>Categories</i>	<i>FG1</i>	<i>FG2</i>
Simplicity of tools (e.g. Canvas, WordPress/Weebly)	5	0
Efficacy in reaching audience (e.g. Facebook)	8	1
Tools well-liked by audience (e.g. Facebook, SMSs)	2	0
Efficacy in reaching a specific person (e.g. LinkedIn Messaging, Facebook Messenger)	---	2
Efficiency (e.g. Facebook Messenger)	---	2
Context of use (overall)		
Within members of the initiative	3	40
External actors	4	4

TABLE IV. DESIRABLE ATTRIBUTES AND FEATURES

<i>Categories</i>	<i>FG1</i>	<i>FG2</i>
Attributes valued in a digital solution		
Simplicity	4	4
Uniqueness	4	0
Integration of several tools	4	0
Up-to-date content	5	0
Sign-up	5	0
Features valued in a digital solution		
Develop synergies with other actors and peers	16	0
Promote the initiative	15	0
Target specific segments of the audience	10	0
Lend information visibility	10	0
Manage regional events agenda	10	0
Link-up with other actors	6	0
Link-up with other peers	8	0
Give and receive endorsement	9	0
Optimised use of current technologies	---	10

TABLE V. FACE TO FACE COMMUNICATION IN FG2

<i>Categories</i>	<i>FG2</i>
Interpersonal communication	
Understand and address market needs	6
Communicate strategic objectives of the initiative	5
Engage community and local partners	5
Create value within communities	4
Strengthen ties	3
Promote values and institutional culture	2

TABLE VI. TYPE OF EXPERIENCE PROMPTED BY TECHNOLOGY USE (DIGITAL TOOLS)

<i>Categories</i>	<i>FG1</i>	<i>FG2</i>
Type of experience prompted by technology use: negative		
Excess of unsorted information (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook, Messenger, SMS, E-mail, Website, Facebook, Virtual agendas)	15	7
Impersonal communication	---	5
Too many digital tools (e.g. WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Slack, Email, Skype, GoToMeeting, GoogleMaps, Facebook Reviews)	10	9
Complexity (e.g. Tools to create websites, Photoshop, MailChimp)	3	---
Unmet extectations (e.g. Facebook Events,)	---	5
Type of experience prompted by technology use: positive		
Simplicity of tools (e.g. Canvas, WordPress/Weebly)	5	0
Efficacy in reaching audience (e.g. Facebook)	8	1
Tools well-liked by audience (e.g. Facebook, SMSs)	2	0
Efficacy in reaching a specific person (e.g. LinkedIn Messaging, Facebook Messenger)	---	2
Efficiency (e.g. Facebook Messenger)	---	2

TABLE VII. TYPE OF EXPERIENCE PROMPTED BY TECHNOLOGY USE (USER EXPERIENCE)

<i>Categories</i>	<i>FG1</i>	<i>FG2</i>
Type of experience prompted by actors: negative		
Type of experience prompted by technology use: negative	4	---
Bureaucracy	4	1
Out-of-date skills (need for capacity building)	4	---
Cultural traits	9	1
Lack of professionalism	4	1
Lack of support to the initiative	---	---
Resources misuse	14	---
Type of experience prompted by actors: positive		
Know how	s/n ^o	---
Support to the iniciative	s/n ^o	---
Flexibility	---	1
Other types of experience (negative or positive)		
Lack of information about events and activities	3	---
Effectiveness	3	---
Lack of resources (e.g. financial)	8	s/n ^o
Organized and complete promotional materials	3	---
Other types of experience (negative or positive)		